

A Study of Relationship between Parent Child Relation and Educational Aspiration of the Students Studying at Secondary Level

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Abstract

The objective of the present study is to find out the relationship between Parent's Child Relation and Educational Aspiration of the Students studying at Secondary level. This is a survey study under descriptive research. For the present study the population was all the male and female studying at Secondary level of Saharanpur District. For the collection of data the researcher administered the parent child relationship scale test by late "NALINI RAO" and Educational Aspiration Scale by "Dr. V.P. Sharma and Dr. Anuradha Gupta". The data collected has been compared by using Pearson's product moment correlation and the results were analyzed and interpretations were drawn. The Findings of the study shows that there is no significant relationship between Parent Child Relation and Educational Aspiration of students at Secondary level.

Keywords: Parent Child Relation, Educational Aspiration, Secondary School Students..

Introduction

Parent Child relationship is one that nurtures the physical, emotional and Social development of the child. It is a unique bond that every parent and child can enjoy. This relationship lays the foundation for the child personality, life choices and overall behaviour. Research on the effects of parental involvement has shown a consistent positive relationship between parent's engagement in their children's education and student outcomes also. Children who have a healthy relationship with their parents are more likely to develop positive relationship with other people around them and children who have unhealthy relationship with their parents they have to face many problems in their life.

Educational Aspiration reflects educational goals that an individual sets for himself / herself. It is also important as it encourages and energizes the individuals to achieve them. Education is an important variable in forming student aspiration in that it serves to help students, become more knowledgeable about the world and more sensitive and understanding of their relationship. "Parenting behaviour & educational support for their children could cultivate children's support for their children could cultivate children's learning habits and affects academic performance".

Shahidul et. al, (2015) studied on social Capital and educational aspiration of students and role of school social capital and family social capital. It concludes that family social capital has more strength to predict the educational aspiration outcome of students as compared to school social capital. Stafford, et. al. (2016) examined parent child relationship quality and positive mental well being using Medical Research Council National Survey of Health and Development data. These results indicated that relationships with fathers results indicated that relationships with fathers and mothers which are supportive, affectionate and allow the child appropriate autonomy may promote good

psychological functioning across life up to and including the seventh decade. Bashir et. al. (2017) studying the educational aspiration with school environment among students. Result indicates that rural and urban students differs each other in school environment but in educational aspiration there is no difference among rural and urban students. Moreover School environment and educational aspiration correlates each other positively. It also concludes that school environment plays a significant role in predicting educational aspiration. Ongoren (2021) investigated parents relationships with their children during the pandemic period . The research findings revealed that the positive aspects of the parent child relationship during the pandemic were stated to be spending time together, sharing, doing activities, and communication, while the negative aspects were reported as social isolation, domestic conflicts and mobile phone addiction.

Significance:

This study was conducted to know how the parent child relationship affects the education of children. This study is not only helpful for the students at school but for parents also. This study focuses on the role of parents in the studies of their children as well as help to maintain a positive and loving relationship with their children which eventually helps in their studies and can help to boost the confidence of their children in every field. So, this study will be beneficial to parents as well as students.

The study will be of great value to the teachers also as they interact with parent's in Parent Teacher Meetings, so they can guide and advise the Parents so as to enhance their cooperation to their children not only in developing healthy, academic and behavioural patterns but also in their all round development.

Statement of the Problem:

A study of Relationship between Parent Child Relation and Educational Aspiration of Students Studying at Secondary Level.

Objectives:

- 1) To find out the relationship between parent child relation and Educational Aspiration of Students Studying at Secondary level.
- 2) To find out the relationship between protecting component of parent child relationship scale and Educational Aspiration of student's studying at secondary level.
- 3) To find out the relationship between symbolic punishment component of parent child relationship scale and educational aspiration of student's studying at secondary level.
- 4) To find out the relationship between rejecting component of parent child relationship and educational aspiration of student's studying at secondary level.
- 5) To find out the relationship between object punishment component of parent child relationship and educational aspiration of student's studying at secondary level.
- 6) To find out the relationship between demanding component of parent child relationship and educational aspiration of student's at secondary level.
- 7) To find out the relationship between indifference component of parent child relationship and educational aspiration of student's at secondary level.
- 8) To find out the relationship between Symbolic Reward Component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of Student's at Secondary level.
- 9) To find out the relationship between loving Component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of Student's at Secondary level.
- 10) To find out the relationship between Object Reward Component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of Student's at Secondary level.
- 11) To find out the relationship between Neglecting Component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of Student's at Secondary level.

Hypotheses:

- 1) There exists no significant relationship between parent child relation and Educational Aspiration of Students Studying at Secondary level. There exists no significant relationship

between protecting component of parent child relationship scale and Educational Aspiration of Student's Studying at Secondary level.

- 2) There exists no significant relationship between Symbolic Punishment Component of Parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of Student's at Secondary level.
- 3) There exists no significant relationship between Rejecting Component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of Student's Studying at Secondary level.
- 4) There exists no significant relationship between object punishment component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of student's studying at Secondary level.
- 5) There exists no significant relationship between Demanding component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of student's at Secondary level.
- 6) There exists no significant relationship between Indifferent component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of student's at Secondary level.
- 7) There exists no significant relationship between symbolic reward component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of student's at Secondary level.
- 8) There exists no significant relationship between loving component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of student's studying at Secondary level.
- 9) There exists no significant relationship between object Reward Component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of student's studying at Secondary level.
- 10) There exists no significant relationship between neglecting component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of student's at Secondary level.

Delimitation:

- 1) The present study has been confined to students studying at secondary level of Uttar Pradesh Board of Education.
- 2) The present study has been confined to students of Saharanpur District of U.P.

Methodology:

The descriptive survey research method has been applied in the study.

Population and Sample:

The population of the present study consisted of all student's studying at Secondary level in Saharanpur District. The sample thus chosen consisted 100 students out of which 50 are male students and 50 are female students.

Variables:

Independent Variables : Parent Child Relationship
Dependent Variables : Educational Aspiration

Tools:

To measure parent child relationship, parent child relationship scale constructed by late Nalini Rao has been used.

To measure Educational Aspiration, Educational Aspiration Scale constructed by Dr. V.P Sharma and Dr. Anuradha Gupta has been used.

Statistical Techniques:

Product moment correlation has been used to study the relationship between Parent Child Relation and Educational Aspiration.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

To test the relationship between the two variables of the study pearson's product moment correlation technique was applied. Significance of correlation coefficient was checked after words to test the significance of the hypotheses. The results obtained are mentioned in the table given below:

TABLE

	Relationship between variables	r-value	Level of Significance
1.	Parent Child Relation & Educational Aspiration	0.1273	NS
2.	Protecting component of parent child relation	-0.0295	NS
3.	Symbolic punishment component of parent child relation & Educational Aspiration	0.1026	NS
4.	Rejecting component of parent child relation & Educational Aspiration.	0.0059	NS
5.	Object Punishment component of Parent child Relation & Educational Aspiration	0.0426	NS
6.	Demanding component of parent child relation & Educational Aspiration.	0.2463	Significant at 0.05
7.	Indifferent component of Parent child Relation & Educational Aspiration	0.1242	NS
8.	Symbolic Reward component of parent child Relation & Educational Aspiration	0.0344	NS
9.	Loving component of Parent Child Relation & Educational Aspiration.	0.0795	NS
10.	Object Reward component of Parent child Relation & Educational Aspiration.	-0.0209	NS
11.	Neglecting component of Parent child Relation & Educational Aspiration.	0.0548	NS

Findings:

The First hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between parent child relation and Educational Aspiration of students studying at Secondary level. Obtained r value is 0.1273. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of r it was found that obtained r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exists between parent child relation and Educational Aspiration of students at Secondary level. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between parent child relation and educational Aspiration of secondary level students is accepted.

The second hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between protecting component of parent child relationship scale and Educational Aspiration of student's studying at secondary level obtained r value is 0.0295. Thus there is negative but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of r at was found that obtained r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between parent child relationship and Educational aspiration of students studying at secondary level. Thus, null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between protecting component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of secondary level students is accepted.

The third hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between symbolic punishment component of parent child Relationship and Educational Aspiration of students at secondary level. Obtained r - value is 0.1026. Thus, there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of r it was found that obtained r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interbreed that no relationship exists between parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of students at secondary level. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between symbolic

punishment component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of secondary level students is accepted.

The Fourth hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between rejecting component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of student's at secondary level obtained r- value is 0.0059. Thus, there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of μ it was found that obtained r- value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no relationship exists between parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of students at secondary level. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between rejecting component of Parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of secondary level students is accepted.

The fifth hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between object Punishment component of Parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of students at secondary level. Obtained r value is 0.0426. Thus, there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of r it was found that obtained μ -value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no relationship exists between parent child relations' and Educational Aspiration of students at secondary level. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between object Punishment component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of Secondary level students is accepted.

The sixth hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between demanding component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of students at secondary level obtained r value is 0.2463. Thus, there is positive but low relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of r it was found that obtained r value is significant at 0.05 level. Hence it may be interpreted that no relationship exists between parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of students at secondary level. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Demanding component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of secondary level students is rejected.

The Seventh hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between indifferent component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of student's at Secondary level. Obtained r-value is 0.1242. Thus, there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables while considering the critical value of r it was found that obtained r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no relationship exists between parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of Student's at Secondary level. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between indifferent component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of secondary school students is accepted.

The eight hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between symbolic reward component of parent child relationship and educational aspiration of students at Secondary level. obtained r value is 0.0344. Thus, there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of r it was found that obtained r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no relationship exists between parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of students at Secondary level. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between symbolic reward component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of secondary school students is accepted.

The ninth hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between loving component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of student's at secondary level obtained r value is 0.0795. Thus, there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of r it was found that obtained r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no relationship exists between parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of students at secondary level. Thus,

null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between loving component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of secondary school student's is accepted.

The tenth hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between object reward component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of student's at secondary level obtained r value is 0.0209. Thus, there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of r it was found that obtained r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no relationship exists between parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of students at secondary level. Thus, null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between object reward component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of secondary school student's is accepted.

The eleventh hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between neglecting component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of student's at secondary level obtained r value is 0.0548. Thus, there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of r it was found that obtained r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no relationship exists between parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of students at secondary level. Thus, null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between neglecting component of parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration of secondary school student's is accepted.

Conclusion:

In this study we find the relationship between parent child relationship and Educational Aspiration based upon the correlation coefficients presented through the table. On the basis of findings of the study it may be concluded that the parent child relationship along with its components has negligible relationship with Educational Aspiration of the students studying at Secondary level.

Implication of the Findings:

This study focuses on the major factor parent child relationship which plays a crucial role in the studies of their children right from their home to their school as well.

Hence this study not only help the individual at school but the parents also. This study focuses on the role of parents in the studies of their children as well as help to maintain a positive and loving relationship with their children which eventually helps in their studies and can help to boost the confidence of their children in every field.

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